

The Relations of Turkic Lexical Units in the Bukhara Oghuz Dialects to Other Turkic Languages and Heritage

Linguistics

Keywords: dialect, historical etymology of words, lexical layer, comparison, synonymic line.

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Abstract

This article explains the use of the Turkic words in the Bukhara Oghuz dialects and compares the Turkic words with other Uzbek dialects and the languages of Turkic language family. There is written the historical etymology of words, lexical layers, comparison, synonymic lines and some features of the vocabulary of the region. Some lexical units in Bukhara's Oghuz dialects are compared with Enasoy, Mahmud Koshghary's "Divan lugat at Turk" and "Attuhfa" monuments. In the lexicon of the region are explained the features of historical-etymology, lexical layers, checking, synonymic series.

The dictionary composition of the Bukhara Oghuz dialects is formed as the lexical-semantic system of the dialect. All lexical units and grammatical texts available in Bukhara's Oghuz Dialects (later BOD) are the essence of this sheet, its own wealth. However, these linguistic unions do not suddenly appear in the vocabulary of the word. The dictionary contains complex stages of development, as well as other Uzbek glossaries.

In order to understand and visualize the evolution of lexical units in BOD, it is necessary to study and analyze the words in the dictionary, to be etymologically subdivided into them. These linguistic actions are carried out to know the origin of the dialect word and to inform them about the scientific community. Most of the lexical units used in the speech of representatives of all Uzbek dialects living in Bukhara region, including the Oghuz dialect, are vague words for almost all Turkic peoples, and most of them can be found in Turkic written monuments. For this reason, N.A.Baskakov's famous work, "Introduction to the Turkic languages", characterized the main lexical fund of Turkic languages as a common unit for all Turkic languages [1, p. 118]. Sh.Shoabdurakhmanov also notes that "because of the fact that the Uzbek language belongs to the family of Turkic languages, many words (Uzbek Uzbek words) specific to the Uzbek language and its dialects have etymological unity with many other words in the dictionary of the Turkic languages" [5, p. 207] in his own work.

Indeed, the words that are used in the Uzbek language and its dialects the *бәш* (bosh), *йүрәк* (yurak), *мән* (men), *быр* (bir), *бәр* (ber), *қарә* (qora), when we compared these words to the Turkmen, Azerbaijani, Turkish, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Karakalpak, Tatar, and other languages, it is possible to see only partial phonetic changes: Tashkent dialects – *бәш*, *йүрәй*, *қарә*, *мән*, *быр*, *бәр*; Ferghana dialects – *бәш*, *йүрәк*, *қарә*, *мен*, *быр*, *бәр*; in Turkmen language – *баши*, *йүрек*, *гара*, *мен*, *бир*, *бар*; Azerbaijan language – *баши*, *үрәк*, *гара*, *мән*, *бир*, *вар*; in Turkish *baş*, *yürek*, *kara*, *ben*, *bir*, *var*; in Kazakh – *бас*, *жүрек*, *қара*, *мен*, *бір*, *бар*; in Kyrgyz – *бас*, *жүрек*,

кара, мен, бир, бар; in Karakalpak – *бас, жүрек, қара, мен, бир, бар*; in Tatar and Bashkir – *баи, йөрәк, кара, мин, бир, бар* and etc.

The original lexic units: *сәккыз* «сақич», *гүн//күн* «күн», *әй* «оу», *гөз // көз, дыл, «til», әйәк* «оуоқ», *бәш* «bosh», *дәг* «tog», *дуз* «tuz» like that nouns; *кычы//кычык* «kichik», *қәтты* «qattiq», *әжы* «achchiq», *ыссы* «issiq», *сүжы* «chuchuk», *йәңы* «yangi», *кетте* «katta», *йәмән* «yomon», *қарры* «qari» like that adjectives, *быр* «bir», *ики* «ikki», *үч* «uch», *дәрт* «to'rt», *бәш* «besh», *алты* «olti», *йеду//йетты* «yetti», *секиз//сәккис* «sakkiz», *докуз* «to'qqiz», *он* «o'n» like that numerals; *дий* «de(moq)», *бол* «bo'l», *қәл* «qol», *чық* «chiq», *гит* «ket», *гәр* «ko'rt», *гәгәр* «ko'kar» like that verbs are shown as an example in the Bukhara Oghuz Dialects dictionary.

Comparing the original Turkic words, which represent the names of the human body and household items, in the Kharezmian Oghuz dialects to the Turkmen, Azerbaijan, Turkish languages, the commonalities between them are evident: BOD, Oghuz, Turkmen, Azerbaijan: *диш*, турк. *Diş* «tish»; BOD, Oghuz *йумрук*, Turkmen *юмрук*, озар. *юмрук*, Turkish *yumruk* «musht»; BOD. *сәкқәл*, Oghuz *сәққәл*, Turkmen *сақгал*, озар. *саггал*, Turkish *sakal* «soqol»; BOD *қуләқ*, Oghuz *қулақ*, Turkmen, Azerbaijan *гулак*, Turkish *kulak* «quloq»; BOD. *қәпәқ*, Oghuz *қанақ*, Turkmen *габак*, Turkish *kapak* «qovoq»; BOD. *додәк*, Oghuz *додақ*, Turkmen *додак*, озар. *додаг*, Turkish *dudak* «dudoq, lab»; BOD, Oghuz *дыл*, Turkmen, Azerbaijan *дил*, Turkish *dil* «til»; BOD *бәғыр*, Oghuz *бағыр*, Turkmen *бағыр*, озар. *бағыр*, Turkish *bagir* «jigar»: BOD. *темәнә*, Oghuz *тәмән*, Turkmen *темен*; Turkish *çuvaldiz* «juvoldiz». BOD *чәнәқ*, Oghuz *чанақ*, Turkmen *чанақ*, озар. *чанаг*, Turkish *çanak*, гагауз. *чанақ* «tovoqcha», BOD. *сусәқ*, Oghuz *сусақ*, гагауз, Turkmen *сусак* «cho'mich» and others. From these linguistic evidences, the wealth of the original Turkic linguistic dictionary is characterized by historically stable and insignificant changes.

These comments are also confirmed by the lexical units listed in the Orkhun-Enasoy monuments and comparable to the rich dictionary dictionary: BOD. *бәшләмәқ*, Enasoy *башламақ* «бошламоқ»; BOD. *эшыт*, Enasoy *эсит* «eshit», BOD. *йош*, Enasoy. *Йаш* «yosh»; BOD, Enasoy *йер* «yer»; BOD. *гүйчлы*, Enasoy *күчлиг* «kuchli»; BOD. *быргә*, Enasoy *бирлә* «birga»; BOD, Enasoy *бәри* «bari»; BOD. *йигирмә // йигирми*, Enasoy *йигирме* «yigirma» (20); BOD. *кәлин //гәлин*, Enasoy *келин* «kelin» ва ш.к. [2, p. 213-215].

Among the original Turkic lexical units in the vocabulary of the word, the interesting and original linguistic evidence for the researchers is extremely diverse and varied. It is possible to know and define the original Turkish linguistic units in this direction only through historical books on Turkish sources. It is the work of Mahmoud Koshgari's "Divan lugat at Turk", which draws the attention of all researchers in terms of the width and richness of these works.

The dialectologist Ahmad Ishaev, who specializes in the study of the Uzbek dialectology, wrote in his book “Divan lugat at Turk”, Mahmud Koshgari, who founded the Comparative Study

of Turkic languages, to many other Turkic languages, including Kipchaq, Oghuz and Karluk-Chigil-Ugur dialects, more specifically, phonetic, grammatical, and especially lexical facts about the dialects of these lines. This is because the majority of the tribes (eg 92 Uzbek ethnicities) participated in the creation of the Uzbek nation and, secondly, the fact that one of the Turkic languages does not have many and diverse forms and dialects like the Uzbek language. These two factors, one of which require the other, have been preserved and recorded in Turkish written monuments in Uzbek, and many linguistic facts common to both general and non-common languages have been preserved "[3, p. 63-67].

Indeed, the lexical units belonging to the original Turkic layer used in the "Divan lugat at Turk" are also used today in Bukhara Oghuz Dialects. We have not yet seen how these linguistic units were used in the Uzbek literary language and Ferghana-Tashkent. According to these facts, it is possible to study these groups of lexical units in groups.

I. Lexical units, which are typical for ancient writing monuments, but are not available in the Uzbek literary language. These lexical units are a) the words that have their synonym in Uzbek: Divan. *aja* «kaft» (Index, 15), BOD. *айа*, Oghuz, Turkmen *а:я* «kaft»; Attuhfa. *эл* (175), Ancient Turkic language. *el* (DTS, 169) «qo'l, kaft», BOD. *эл // ал*, Turkmen *эл*, Oghuz *эл* «qo'l»; Divan. *Жумуртға* «tuxum» (Index, 140), BOD. Oghuz *йумурта*, Turkmen *юмуртга* «tuxum»; Divan. *jitī: jīmūmī* «o'tkirlatdi, charxlatdi» (Index, 131), BOD. *Иттик* «o'tkir», Turkmen *йити* «o'tkir»; Divan. *kizlādi* «yashirdi» (Index, 160), BOD, Oghuz *гизләмәк*, Turkmen *гизлемек* «yashirmoq»; Divan. *Jitti* «yo'qoldi» (Index, 134), BOD. *йитти*, Oghuz *йытты*, Turkmen *йитди* «yo'qoldi»; Divan. *Chirildi* «bog'landi» (Index 331), BOD. *чигилди*, Oghuz *чийилди*, Turkmen *чигилди* «bog'landi» and others. b) Uzbek literary language is not synonymous with the words: Divan. *Añiz* «don ekinlari o'rib olingan yer» (Index, 20), BOD. *Ангара* «hosili yig'ib olingan dala». This lexical unity seems to have been interpreted as a *энгар//энгор//эңән* in the Uzbek language in Tajikistan as "harvested crops" [4, p. 54-56] . Divan. *Атис* «the crop between the two arcs» (Index, 27), BOD. *Атыз*, Oghuz, Turkmen, Karakalpak *атыз* «cultivated field, cultivated fruit crops» and others.

II. The original Turkic words that change in their meaning. Some of the lexical units used in the ancient Turkic written monuments are now being used for some partial change in terms of meaning from the speech of the BOD. This process should be regarded as "the result of our language's developmental laws, because of the age, these words are gaining new significance and increasingly moving away from their meaning" [4, p. 55]. Here are some examples of lexical units: Divan. *Їмир* «қош қорайган пайт (ўғузча)» (Index, 92). BOD. *Имир* "it is a bit of a rainstorm". This word in the Uzbek dialects is used as a *имир* (Khazarasp) «дим» (O'zshl, 116), *ымырдуман* (Beruniy, Biybozor) «tuman, qoratutun» (O'zshl, 122; E.O'rozov, 92), Turkmen *үмүр* «steam mixture» (TDS, 684). Divan. *Адаш* «friend», *адашлиқ* «friendship» (Index, 11-12), in the BOD and other dialects used as a meaning *эдәш//адәш*; the appeal of such people to each other» (O'TIL, II, 1, 39). Compare: Turkmen *аташ* «адаш» (ТДС, 57), Turk *adaş* «адаш» (TRS,

25); Divan. *ақур*. «отхона» (Index, 31), BOD and other Uzbek dialects are used as a meaning *ахыр//ахур//эхур*, this word is mean «The livestock (sheep, goats, cattle, horses) is a feeding device» (O‘TIL, II, 3, 161). The meaning of the Uzbek language and its passages must have passed the Persian-Tajik language. The word "hothouse" in Persian-Tajik is represented by lexical units such as a *саусхона, аспхона, ахтахона, тавила* (Rustadjsl, 409), and feeding on livestock is given by the word *оx* (Rubinchik, 1, 56; Rustadjsl, 1240); Divan. *Cöl* «weat» (Index, 229), in the BOD and other dialects the word *сел*, in the Uzbek literary language you can meet like that form *sel*, and it is mean the water of meat and blood (O‘TIL, II, 3, 476). Divan *эка* «sister»; «older sister» (DLT, III, 13; Index, 40), in the BOD and other Uzbek dialects the word *эка* is used as a mean «An elderly parent (in relation to his / her little ones)» in the Uzbek language. But in the Oghuz dialects of Uzbek language the word *эка* as a mean «father» (Xsh, 22), as well as, in the Oghuz dialects the word *эка* is synonym with the lexical unit *а:за*, it is mean in Russian *старший брат*. But in the Turkmen dialects depending on Oghuz group’s language, for example, in the dialects *yemrali, ota, arsari* the word *эке* is mean «older sister», in the Kirach dialects *эке* is mean «brother», in the Nokhur and Murcha dialects the word *эке* is mean «papa». In the Turkmen literary language the word *экежи* is mean «*qaynegachi*» (TDS, 799).

In conclusion, lexical units belonging to the original Turkic dialect have a characteristic feature in the Bukhara-Oguz dialect, historically stable and undergone. In this regard, original Turkish words in our subject matter are the common wealth of the BOD, the broader Uzbek and Turkic languages. Mahmud Koshgari's "Divan lugat at Turk", the common Turkic layer in the languages of the BOD and Oguz group, confirms that the linguistic phenomena of Oguz are still living and immortal. Historical and comparative study of the Divon and the linguistic facts in all Uzbek sheets confirms that the Uzbek literary language is lexically based on all folk folklore, not in any language [5, p. 316].

References

1. Baskakov N.A. Vvedeniye v izucheniye tyurkskix yazikov. – M., «Visshaya shkola», 1969.
2. Batmanov I.A., Aragachi Z.B., Babushkin G.F. Sovremennaya i drevnyaya Yeniseyka. – Frunze: Ilim, 1962.
3. Ishayev A. Devonu lug‘otit turk va o‘zbek shevalari // O‘zbek tili va adabiyoti, 1971. – №5. – B. 63-67.
4. SHERALIYEV E. Shevalardagi umumturkiy so‘zlar // O‘zbek tili va adabiyoti, 1990. 2-son. – B. 54-56.
5. Shoabdurahmonov Sh. O‘zbek adabiy tili va o‘zbek xalq shevalari. Toshkent: Fan, 1962.
6. Odilovna, R. M. (2018). The Role and Status of Linguistic Markers in the System of Symbols. ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, 7(7), 29-34.
7. Raufovna, S. R. (2018). The Problems in Researching Homogenized Sentences. ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, 7(7), 35-44.

8. Dilnoza, Y. (2018). About Conducting Research on the Subject of Ornithological Terms in Uzbek Language. ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, 7(7), 53-61.
9. Shernazarov, A. (2018). Social-Psychological Basics of Bilingual Folklore Genesis in Kashkadarya Oasis. ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, 7(7), 45-52.
10. Sattarovich, R. N. (2018). Grammatical Forms Specific to Verb Group in Uzbek Dialects (In the Sample of Dialects of Navoi Region). ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, 7(6), 60-65.
11. Khursand, T. (2018). Synharmonism of Inter-Components of the Literary Style Evolution in the Uzbek Literature. ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, 7(6), 66-72.
12. Axronkulovna, J. M. (2018). Feelings of Artistic Expressions and Admittances. ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, 7(6), 80-83.
13. Djalalovna, H. A. (2018). Textual Analysis of the Abdurauf Fitrat's Work "Oldest Turkic Literature Samples". ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, 7(5).
14. Dilnoza, D. (2018). Comments on Studying Linguopoetic Properties of Terms in a Textual Aspect. ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, 7(5).
15. Uralovna, J. F. (2018). Definition Criteria of Synonyms in the Uzbek Language. ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, 7(5).
16. Raufovna, S. R. (2018). Peculiarities of Synonymic Sentence in the Uzbek Language. ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, 7(4), 66-71.
17. Akmalovna, S. D. (2018). Place of Basic Words and Phrases in Reconstruction of an Ideological Enthusiasm of Poetical Work in Translation. ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, 7(4), 72-77.
18. Kuzibaevna, G. H. (2018). Some Notes of Literary-Critical Problems in the Uzbek Literature. ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, 7(2), 27-33.
19. Abdurahimova, R. D. (2017). Cognitive Features of Metaphoric Euphemisms used by the Uzbeks. ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, 6(11), 43-49.
20. Muhammadievich, M. B. (2017). Compound Terms Formed on the Basis of Similarity Association. ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, 6(10), 33-41.
21. Abdullaevna, R. F. (2017). Narrative and Methodical Trends in the Uzbek Literature. ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, 6(10), 71-79.
22. Pazlitdinova, N. (2017). The Linguistic Status of Phytonyms. ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, 6(9), 109-116.
23. Isakovna, T. N. (2017). The Symbol of Mirror and its Main Poetic Functions in Fairy Tales. ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association for Anglo-American Studies, 6(2), 7-11.

Abbreviation

- Attuhfa** – Attuhfatuz zakiyatu fillug‘atit turkiya. T., «Fan», 1968.
- Devon** – Devonu lug‘otit turkda.
- DLT** – Devonu lug‘otit turk. Uch jild. T., «Fan», 1960–1962 (tarjimon va nashrga tayyorlovchi S. Mutallibov).
- DTS** – Drevnetyurkskiy slovar. L., «Nauka», 1969.
- Index** – Devonu lug‘otit turk. Index-lug‘at. T., «Fan», 1967.
- Ishayev** – Ishayev A. Qoraqalpog‘istondagi o‘zbek shevalari. T., «Fan», 1977.
- Rubinchik, 1** – Persidsko-russkiy slovar. V dvux tomax. M., «Sovetskaya ensiklopediya», 1970 (Rukovoditel Y.A. Rubinchik).
- Ruskksl** – Russko-karakalpakskiy slovar. M., «Sovetskaya ensiklopediya», 1967.
- Rustadjsl** – Russko-tadjikskiy slovar. M., «Russkiy yazik», 1985.
- Rustatsl – Russko-tatarskiy slovar. M., «Russkiy yazik», 1984.**
- Rustursl** – Russko-turetskiy slovar. M., «Sovetskaya ensiklopediya», 1972.
- TDS** – Tyrkmen diliniñ sozlygi. Ashgabat, «Ilim», 1962.
- TRS – Turetsko-russkiy slovar. M., «Russkiy yazik», 1977.**
- T.N.** – Nafasov T. Qashqadaryo o‘zbek xalq so‘zlari. T., «Muharrir», 2011.
- XSH** – Abdullayev F. Xorazm shevalari. T., «Fan», 1961.
- O‘zxshl** – O‘zbek xalq shevalari lug‘ati. T., «Fan», 1971.
- O‘zshl** – O‘zbek shevalari leksikasi». T., «Fan», 1966.
- E. O‘rozov** – O‘rozov E. Janubiy Qoraqalpog‘istondagi o‘zbek shevalari. T., «Fan» 1978.
- O‘TIL, II** – O‘zbek tilining izohli lug‘ati (Besh jildli). T., «O‘zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi» Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, 2006–2008.